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Impact Factor: 1.13

A STUDY OF DEPRECIATION AS PER COMPONENT ACCOUNTING APPROACH UNDER COMPANIES ACT 2013

Dr. Soheli Ghose

Asst. Prof. Department of Commerce (Morning)
St. Xavier's College, Kolkata

ABSTRACT

Objectives: The objectives are to analyse the concept of Component Accounting Approach, the changes in depreciation with respect to Companies Act 2013 with numerical examples and illustrations and the Industry impact of component accounting.

Research Methodology: The data has been collected from secondary sources of authentic websites, reports, journals and books. The study undertaken is Descriptive research. The study of the Schedule II and the Companies Act 2013 as a whole is theoretical in nature. The source includes a collection of Reports by competent Chartered Accountants and Committees as well as websites on the internet.

Findings: The Summary of Component Accounting is as follows. Under this approach, first split the fixed asset into various identifiable parts to the extent possible. The identified parts are then grouped together if they have the same or similar useful life. No need to identify and depreciate insignificant parts as separate components; rather, they can be combined together in the remainder of the asset or with the principal asset. Identification of significant parts is a matter of judgment and decided on case-to-case basis. Identification of separate parts of an asset and determination of their useful life is not merely an accounting exercise; rather, it involves technical expertise. Hence, involve technical experts to determine the parts of an asset. If the useful life of the component is lower than the useful life of the principal assets as per Schedule II, such lower useful should be used. In reverse scenario higher useful life for a component can be used only when management intends to use the component even after expiry of useful life for the principal asset.

Limitations: The research is descriptive in nature and an empirical analysis can be done in future. Also the scope of the theoretical study can be extended to Component Accounting as per Companies Act 2013.

Practical Implications: *Mining and Construction:* Assets in Mining and Construction industry include heavy duty trucks, vehicles, dozers, excavators, loaders & unloaders, tunnelling machinery, etc. These items will have to be broken in to their components. *Commodity manufacturing Industry - Crude, Ore, Power:* Various facilities that can be identified as first level components such as Water, treatment, Gas tapping, Conveyors, Turbines, Rooters, Shafts, Grids ,Ovens, Casters, Moulds, Furnaces, Rolling mills, etc. *Shipping Industry:* A modern ship includes a fair component of electronic and automatic control systems. Entities will have to carry out a detailed exercise and use its judgement for capitalising each component. *Hotel Industry:* A restaurant maintains a minimum stock of silverware and dishes. Any increase or decrease is accounted as consumption in profit and loss account. Moreover, Schedule XIV does not lay down any rate for depreciating such items and hence companies in India adopt inventory and consumption approach to account these items.

Originality and Value: The paper includes practical examples of organizations and numerical examples of the Sections of Component Accounting. It also includes Literature Review relating to component accounting. It highlights the differences between the treatment of depreciation as per Accounting Standards and IND AS.

Key Words: Cost, Component Accounting, Residual value, Shift, Useful life.

Introduction: All fixed assets except the value of land decreases with the passage of time. The value of these assets decrease each year. Such gradual reduction or decrease in the value of fixed assets for the purpose of earning revenue is called depreciation. Depreciation is closely related with the determination of profit or loss for the period. Unless depreciation is charged to the revenues, the true income of the business cannot be ascertained properly. As such, depreciation is a revenue expense. Fixed assets are also called depreciable assets. The characteristics of depreciable assets are as follows.

* The expected life of the asset is more than one accounting period.

- * Those assets have a limited useful life.
- * Those assets are held by the business for use in production of goods and services.
- * Those assets are not for the purpose of sale in the ordinary course of business.

The cost of fixed asset indicates 'the price for the future service of the assets'. It is necessary to spread its cost over a number of years during which benefit of the asset is received. This process of allocating the cost of fixed assets is termed as 'depreciation'. The recent enactment of the Companies Act, 2013 is a dawn of a new era. After bringing far-reaching changes in various areas, the spectrum of financial reporting has widened and brings higher responsibilities to those associated with financial reporting, be it the auditors or the management. One such area is Depreciation.

Literature Review: In his address delivered before the convention of central water works association, Detroit, *Walford Erikson* basically emphasized the need of providing depreciation in the books of accounts to present a true and fair view of the financial books of accounts. Also the idea was to show case how the value of an asset should be rationally depreciated so as to replace such asset in the long run .This also emphasized on numerous factors that were responsible for depreciating the value of assets , to name a few , reasons like efflux of time , obsolescence , change in technology etc. *Hercules Bantas*, in his book looks at the various types of fixed assets and the role they play in financial reporting. Topics covered include depreciation, disposal of assets, and gain/loss on disposal. *Subrata Kar* in his book deals with the depreciation methods and procedures to be followed as per the companies act 2013.The book has been specially designed keeping in mind the various amendments as per the new Companies Act 2013, attempts has been made to incorporate all possible changes of the new act and its impact on various sectors. *Samuelson* has worked on how "income" should be defined if present discounted valuations of all assets, and therefore all optimization decisions. *Darr, Argote and Epple* in their paper examined the acquisition, depreciation and transfer of knowledge acquired through learning by doing in service organizations. They also highlighted the accurate ways of computing depreciations in the Service organisations.

Objectives of the study:

1. To analyse the concept of Component Accounting Approach.
2. To analyze the changes in depreciation with respect to Companies Act 2013 with numerical examples and illustrations.
3. To analyse the Industry impact of component accounting.

Research Methodology and Data Collection: The data has been collected from secondary sources of authentic websites, reports, journals and books. The study undertaken is Descriptive research. The study of the Schedule II and the Companies Act 2013 as a whole is theoretical in nature. The source includes a collection of Reports by competent Chartered Accountants and Committees as well as websites on the internet.

Analysis and Inferences:

COMPONENT APPROACH/ COMPONENT ACCOUNTING: It is a method in which the parts or sections of a property are individually depreciated at different rates .

Useful life specified in Part C of the Schedule is for whole of the asset.

Useful life of significant part shall be determined separately:

- a) Where cost of a part of the asset is significant to total cost of the asset
- b) Useful life of that part is different from the useful life of the remaining asset

Some industries the determination is simple while some industry it is complex process.

Schedule II states that the useful life specified is for whole of the asset. However, where cost of a part of the asset is significant to total cost of the asset and the part's useful life is different from the useful life of the remaining asset, useful life of that significant part shall be depreciated separately.

This method of breaking a fixed asset into components for depreciation purposes is known as the 'component approach' to compute depreciation.

Companies will now have to estimate the useful life of each such component (in case it is not provided in Schedule II) and depreciate the cost of that specific component over the estimated useful life. To apply the component approach, it is crucial to identify the various significant parts of an asset.

There are two reasons for identifying the parts:

Depreciation, and The replacement of parts

Generally, it is done by looking for items that will require replacement before the end of the asset's useful life, and to treat these items as separate components. Upon replacement of a part, the remaining book value of the replaced part is derecognised and the cost of the new part recognised, irrespective of whether the replaced part was depreciated separately or not.

There is no minimum requirement for the number of parts of a fixed asset that should be identified. The number of parts may vary depending on the nature and the complexity of the fixed asset. Ind AS 16 requires each significant part of a fixed asset to be depreciated separately. Significant parts which have the same useful life and depreciation method may be depreciated together. Additionally, such parts that are individually not significant are combined in the remainder and are depreciated together

Componentization requires professional judgment. In many situations, a company may not have a good understanding of the cost of the individual components purchased. In that case, the cost of individual components should be estimated based on reference to:

Current market prices (if available), discussion with experts in valuation, or use of other reasonable approaches. It might also be considered necessary to request an expert opinion (for example, construction experts) in order to determine the parts of a fixed asset. This will also depend on the size of the organization and whether the component and related depreciation will have a material effect on the financial statements.

For instance, the following practices are commonly used to identify the parts of a building: Exterior walls, Interior walls, Windows, Roof, Staircase, Elevators, and Air condition, Heating System, Water System, Electrical system and Major inspections.

The following can also help in identifying components:

Reviewing plant maintenance programs may help. If the replacement of a component is significant enough to be listed on maintenance schedule, it may have a cost that is significant in comparison to the total cost of the asset; Reviewing historical retirement patterns to evaluate what constitutes a component is needed. Analyzing major capital expenditures may help.

SUMMARY OF COMPONENT ACCOUNTING:

- ▶ Under this approach, first split the fixed asset into various identifiable parts to the extent possible.
- ▶ The identified parts are then grouped together if they have the same or similar useful life.
- ▶ No need to identify and depreciate insignificant parts as separate components; rather, they can be combined together in the remainder of the asset or with the principal asset.
- ▶ Identification of significant parts is a matter of judgment and decided on case-to-case basis.

- ▶ Identification of separate parts of an asset and determination of their useful life is not merely an accounting exercise; rather, it involves technical expertise.
- ▶ Hence, involve technical experts to determine the parts of an asset.
- ▶ If the useful life of the component is lower than the useful life of the principal assets as per Schedule II, such lower useful should be used. In reverse scenario higher useful life for a component can be used only when management intends to use the component even after expiry of useful life for the principal asset.

INDUSTRY IMPACT OF COMPONENT ACCOUNTING: The concept of component accounting has a great impact on various sectors of the industries, few of them are discussed in the following light :

Mining and Construction: Assets in Mining and Construction industry include heavy duty trucks, vehicles, dozers, excavators, loaders & unloaders, tunnelling machinery, etc.

Heavy duty machineries are made up of various assembled parts which are high in value and also have a different useful life as compared to the other parts such as chassis, rollers, body, electrical systems, etc. These items will have to be broken in to their components.

Entities will also have to estimate mine restoration liabilities and capitalise with the initial cost of the mine.

Commodity manufacturing Industry - Crude, Ore, Power: Various facilities that can be identified as first level components such as Water, treatment, Gas tapping, Conveyors, Turbines, Rooters, Shafts, Grids ,Ovens, Casters, Moulds, Furnaces, Rolling mills, etc.. More often one component that is left out in the analysis is the Pipelines, which have material value and different useful life .

Entities will need to estimate its asset retirement obligations at the time of initial capitalisation.

Shipping Industry: Main parts of a ship include hull and engine. Further, hull is made up of deck, chassis, propeller, funnel, stern and super structure. A modern ship includes a fair component of electronic and automatic control systems. Entities will have to carry out a detailed exercise and use its judgement for capitalising each component.

Hotel Industry: A restaurant maintains a minimum stock of silverware and dishes. Some entities treat cutlery, crockery, linen, etc, as stores and spares and group them under inventory. Any increase or decrease is accounted as consumption in profit and loss account. Moreover, Schedule XIV does not lay down any rate for depreciating such items and hence companies in India adopt inventory and consumption approach to account these items.

Notes to the Schedule II and Practical examples: The most important and challenging aspect of Schedule II is the effect to be given in the books of account on the date of transition, i.e. 1st April, 2014.

Note 7 to Part C of Schedule II prescribes the transitional effect as follows:-

From the date this Schedule comes into effect, the carrying amount of the asset as on that date-

- (a) Shall be depreciated over the remaining useful life of the asset as per this Schedule;
- (b) After retaining the residual value, shall be recognized in the opening balance of retained earnings where the remaining useful life of an asset is nil.”

Two possibilities regarding the assets as on 1st April, 2014 in context of the above note:

1. Asset's remaining useful life as per Schedule II is nil:

In that case, as per Note 7(b), the carrying amount has to be adjusted in the opening balance of retained earnings in the balance sheet after retaining the residual value.

2. Asset's remaining useful life is as per Schedule II is not nil:

If one reads Note 7, specifically clause (a), then one has to continue depreciating the balance as on 1st April, 2014 systematically over the remaining useful life after recalculating the rate of depreciation. In that case, no effect of restating the carrying amount will be needed to be given. Depreciation should be provided at a rate prescribed as under based on the remaining useful life of the Asset.

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES FOR CALCULATION OF DEPRECIATION:-

Rate of Depreciation under WDV Method:

$$R = (1 - (s/c) (1/n)) \times 100$$

Where R = Rate of Depreciation (in %),

n = Useful life of the asset (in years)

s = Scrap value at the end of useful life of the asset (i.e. max 5% of cost)

c= Cost of the asset

Example: note 7(a):-

Asset: Plant & Machinery; Original Cost: Rs. 1,00,000

Useful Life and rate of Depreciation as per Old Provisions: 20 years & 13.91%

Useful Life and rate of Depreciation as per New Provisions

Useful Life and rate of Depreciation as per New Provisions: 15 Years & 18.10%

Expired Life: 5 years

Accumulated Depreciation for 5 years: 52,711/-

Now the Carrying Amount as on 01.04.2014 will be 47,289/- (1,00,000-52,711)

Remaining Useful life as on 01.04.2014 as per new provisions 10 years (15 years – Expired Life)

Rate of Depreciation on the basis of remaining useful life i.e.10 years is 25.89%

Example: note 7(b):-

Asset: Plant & Machinery; Original Cost: Rs.1,00,000

Useful Life and rate of Depreciation as per Old Provisions: 20 years & 13.91%

Useful Life and rate of Depreciation as per New Provisions: 15 Years & 18.10%

Expired Life: 16 years

Accumulated Depreciation for 16 years: 90,896/-

Now the Carrying Amount as on 01.04.2014 will be 9,104/- (1,00,000-90,896)

Remaining useful life as on 01.04.2014 as per new provisions is nil (15 years – Expired Life)

In such a case Note 7(b) comes into picture and the entry on 01.04.2014 would be

Retained Earnings Dr 4,104

To Plant & Machinery 4,104

(Being shortfall in the depreciation consequent upon change in the useful life of asset provided for after retaining residual value of 5% charged against opening balance of retained earnings)

Residual value should not be more than 5% of cost of asset i.e. Rs. 5,000 and accordingly the amount to be adjusted shall be Rs. 4,104 (9,104-5,000).

Limitations of the Study

The research is descriptive in nature and an empirical analysis can be done in future. Also the scope of the theoretical study can be extended to Component Accounting as per Companies Act 2013.

Conclusion: The component accounting shall be voluntary in respect of the financial year commencing on or after the 1st April, 2014 and mandatory for financial statements in respect of financial years commencing on after the 1st April, 2015. The application of component accounting is likely to cause significant change in accounting for replacement costs. Currently, companies need to expense such costs in the year of incurrence. Under the component accounting, companies will capitalize these costs, with consequent expensing of net carrying value of the replaced part.

It is not clear how component accounting will work for class (iii) companies. Since depreciation for the principal asset under the Schedule is meant to be the minimum amount, a component can certainly have a shorter life than the principal asset. However, it may not be possible for a component to have a longer life than what is prescribed under the Schedule for the principal asset.

Under the Schedule, depreciation is provided on historical cost or the amount substituted for the historical cost. Therefore, in case of revaluation, depreciation will be based on the revalued amount. Consequently, the ICAI guidance may not apply and full depreciation on the revalued amount is expected to have significant negative impact on the statement of profit and loss. In such a case, the amount standing to the credit of revaluation reserve may be transferred directly to the general reserve. A company may transfer whole of the reserve when the asset is sold or disposed of. Alternatively, it may transfer proportionate amount as the asset is depreciated.

References:

Books and Journals:

1. **Bantas (2013)**, *Fixed Assets and Depreciation (Financial Accounting Basics Book 1)*, Reluctant Geek Smashword Edition.
2. **Kar (2013)**, *Corporate Depreciation Accounting*, Sbs publishers.
3. **Samuelson (1964)**, "Tax deductibility of economic depreciation to insure invariant valuations", *The Journal of political economy*, 72, no. 6 December Issue.

4. **Taylor and Francis (1925)**, “A general mathematical theory of depreciation, H Hotelling” - *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 20, 151.
5. **Darer, Argote and Epple (1995)**, “The acquisition, transfer, and depreciation of knowledge in service organizations”, 41, 11.
6. Companies Act, 2013 Bare Act
7. Erikson (1912), address delivered before the convention of central water works association.

Websites:

1. 27th January 2016, http://www.icaai.org/new_post.html?post_id=11504&c_id=240
2. 12th February 2016, <http://taxguru.in/company-law/application-scheduleii-companies-act-2013-contradiction-as6.html>
3. 16th February 2016 , <http://www.mca.gov.in/SearchableActs/Schedule2.htm>
4. 17th February 2016, <http://scn.sap.com/docs/DOC-57392>
5. 27th February 2016, <http://taxguru.in/company-law/depreciation-schedule-ii-companies-act-2013.html>
6. 4th March, <https://www.kpmg.com/IN/en/IssuesAndInsights/first-notes/Documents/First-Notes-24April2015>.
7. 4th March, <http://www.ey.com/Publication/vwLUAssets/EY-depreciation-of-fixed-assets/%24FILE/EY-depreciation-of-fixed-assets>.
8. 4th March, <http://www.charteredclub.com/depreciation-as-per-companies-act/>